

KNOWLEDGE AND EXPRESSED PRACTICES OF STAFF NURSES TOWARDS DISASTER PREPAREDNESS IN THE MEDEOR HOSPITAL, MANESAR, HARYANA, INDIA

*¹Fazl Ur Rahman, Dr. Poonam Sharma², Sakshi Sood³ and Ruchika Singh⁴

^{1,3}Department of Medical Surgical Nursing at Faculty of Nursing & Midwifery, Metro college of Health Science and Research, Gr. Noida (UP).

²Associate Professor Department of Psychiatric Nursing, Amity College of Nursing, Amity University Haryana.

⁴Department of Medical Surgical Nursing at Faculty of Nursing & Midwifery, SGT University, Gurugram, Haryana.

Received date: 30 July 2021

Revised date: 20 August 2021

Accepted date: 10 September 2021

*Corresponding Author: Fazl Ur Rahman

Department of Medical Surgical Nursing at Faculty of Nursing & Midwifery, Metro college of Health Science and Research, Gr. Noida (UP).

Email Id: fazlwani2@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Background: Disasters may be defined as "any destructive events that disrupt the normal functioning of a community". **Aim:** This study is aimed to assess the level of nurses' knowledge and practices regarding disasters preparedness. **Methods:** Quantitative, descriptive, survey approach was used to assess nurse's knowledge and practices among 20 random staff nurses of Medeor Hospital, Manesar, Haryana by using socio demographic data sheet, Descriptive statistics and Chi square test. **Results:** In overall view of the present study findings: the mean percentage of the knowledge score was 21.60% and the mean percentage of the practice score was 16.50%. The study findings revealed that knowledge and practices of disaster preparedness was average level with highly significant differences $P \leq .000$. **Conclusion:** Based on the present study results; it can be concluded that the level of knowledge and practice were average regarding disaster preparedness and neutral familiarity with emergency preparedness were found. Thus, an integration of clearly titled theory and practice teaching courses about disaster preparedness into nursing curriculum are needed and provided in respect to their knowledge and training preferences. Further, follow up research are necessary for maximizing nursing education and nursing quality in these critical areas applied to healthcare and community setting.

INDEXTERMS: Pilot study, disaster, preparedness, staff nurses, knowledge and expressed practices, earthquake, hospitals.

INTRODUCTION

A disaster is an incident that can cause massive damage and disruption. Disasters are common worldwide occurrence now a days. These events have dramatically bad impact on many people, to kill and injure them, damage and destroy their houses, health system, and interrupt their lifeline. This is big loss of any county who face the disaster.

Florence's nightingale showed the world that nurses play leading role in front line of the disasters and public health. The public health nurses bring new skills and knowledge in each phase of disaster like preparedness, response and rehabilitation. Nurses are the key person working in the hospital emergencies and any disasters and prepared a plan to prevent the hazards. During the disaster the first contender are the nurses, who have enough knowledge and skill related to the disasters and

disaster management.

Disaster preparedness is very much important for minimize the damaging effects of disasters and emergencies. Emergency preparedness is defined as appropriate knowledge, skills and action which are required to respond and ready for threat which may be actually and suspicious.

Disaster preparedness for nurses is also focused by the International Nursing Coalition for Mass Casualty Education (INCMCE) (2003) that said that overall world wide the nurses' knowledge and skill should be maximum to deal with different emergency situations. It is said that the nurses who are prepared for emergencies can play better and efficient role in disasters. Disaster preparedness has 4 stages which are precaution, preparedness, response and rehabilitation.

There is growing interest in the effectiveness of disaster preparedness in hospitals. Although several studies have examined staff nurses' preparedness perceptions, a better understanding of factors that may influence actual preparedness is needed.

Disaster management does not avert or eliminate the threats; instead, it focuses on creating plans to decrease the effect of disasters. It is essential for an organization to include procedures for determining whether an emergency situation has occurred and at what point an emergency management plan should be activated.

World Disasters Report 2015 reported 317 natural disasters worldwide in 2014, affecting 94 countries. About 48% of all disasters occurred in Asia in 2014. Asia had a region that mostly effected by the disasters estimated that 90.13% of worldwide disasters come across the Asia.

Emergency preparedness is comprehensive skills, abilities, knowledge, and actions that are needed to respond and prepare for a threat, actual or suspected, chemical, radiological, nuclear, biological, or explosive in nature. During major disaster events, the demand for nursing staff is much greater than the demands for any other healthcare professionals. Nurses should anticipate an expanded role during disaster events to include caring for the sick and injured, infection control, contingency planning to prevent further damage, triage, mass immunizations, mass evacuations, and treatment for mass casualties.

The ICN Framework of Disaster Nursing Competencies and recognized an accelerated and present need to build capacities of nurses at all levels in order to "safeguard populations, limit injuries and deaths, and maintain health system functioning and community well-being, in the midst of continued health threats and disasters"

India is a developing country and developing countries are more prone of disasters because lack of disasters preparedness. Disasters can be owing to natural events (such as storms, drought, earthquakes, and disease epidemic), or technological events (such as explosions, structure collapse, and radiological accidents) or civil/political events (such as strikes, terrorism, and biological warfare). Unfortunately, India is not only facing natural disasters but also under the influence of terrorism. During 2015-16, a total of 1,025 terror attacks were recorded, resulting in hundreds of people dead and thousands of people injured. Terrorism is a major problem faced by the India that affects the basic structure of the country and lives of the citizens.

In 2009, the World Health Organization (WHO) and the International Council of Nurses (ICN) released the ICN Framework of Disaster Nursing abilities, which describes the basic skills and knowledge are necessary for the registered nurses to be think competent in disasters

management.

Discuss in this study that there is need for further researches to determine the current knowledge of nurses regarding the emergency preparedness and should design the educational programs to enhance their knowledge and some educational program should be the part of their curriculum. Nurses plays very important role in the any disasters and emergency. The knowledge and practices of nurses are also play key role in managing the disasters and in the preparedness of emergency.

Problem Statement

Disasters happen frequently now a days especially in Asia. India is the most probably exposed to being attacked of disasters due to its atmosphere and environmental factors. According to record India experience number of deaths due to natural disasters across India. In 2008 number of deaths were 3,746, in 2009 number of deaths were 3,746, in 2014 number of deaths due to disaster were 5,677 and thousands are under the influenced of disasters. It is observed through reading articles that there is limited preparedness and management plans in the government as well as private hospitals. Nurses has insufficient knowledge and practices regarding the disaster preparedness which is a week point of the staff nurses. There is no educational programme to enhance their knowledge and as well as their practices.

The research question of this study is that what is the knowledge and practice of nurses who are working in the emergency department about the disaster preparedness.

Aim of the study

Disasters happen is to assess the level of staff nurse's knowledge and practices regarding disaster preparedness in Medeor Hospital, Manesar, Haryana.

The objectives of this study were: 1. To assess the knowledge of staff nurses regarding disaster preparedness. 2.To assess the expressed practices of staff nurses towards disaster preparedness. 3.To find out the association of knowledge with demographic variables. 4.To find out the association of practice with demographic variables. 5.To find out the correlation of knowledge and expressed practices of staff nurses regarding disaster preparedness.

METHODOLOGY

To conduct this study the Quantitative descriptive cross sectional study design was used. The study is conducted in Medeor hospital Manesar, Gurugram, Haryana (122052). A Non probability Convenience Sampling technique was used. An online Self-administered questionnaire (SAQ) with close ended questions and Self-structured checklist (SSC) was developed by using Google forms. The link of the questionnaire was sent through e-mails, WhatsApp and other social media to the contacts of the investigators. The participants were

encouraged to participate in the survey. Thus, the link was forwarded to staff nurses apart from the first point of contact and so on. As they receive the form by clicking the link, the participants got auto directed to the information about the study and informed consent. Initially they have given their consent for the survey and then filled the demographic variables. Afterwards, a set of several questions appeared sequentially, which the participants were to answer. Participants with access to the internet could participate in the study. I was able to collect 20 responses from the selected hospitals.

Inclusion criteria

- Staff nurses who are working in the selected hospitals in Gurugram.
- Available during the time of data collection.
- The participants who was willing to participate in the study.
- Able to understand English language

Exclusion criteria

Paramedical staffs were excluded

Ethical Consideration

An informed written consent form was taken by the subject before data collection. All the subjects were ensured that confidentiality and anonymity was maintained throughout the study.

Permission was obtained from Institutional Ethical Committee to carry out the study. Written permission was also obtained from Director of the respective hospitals before data collection.

Prior to administration to tools, subjects were given information verbally and in writing about the nature of the study and inform them about their right not to participate, to withdraw at any time without explanation.

Subjects were not any under any obligation to give consent for participating in this study. All the questions and queries were discussed and sort out before actual data collection.

Tools

Two tools were developed and utilized by the researcher for data collection, after reviewing the related literatures. There are 3 broad categories:

- Demographic information.
- Knowledge on disaster preparedness.
- Practices on disaster preparedness.

The demographical data include age, gender, clinical years of experience, qualification and department. And knowledge-based questionnaire includes 35 questions covered about the disaster management and preparedness. The practices questionnaire included the 25 questions about disasters drill done at hospital, what type of drill is done, ongoing training, how often, disasters plan update and how often developed.

The data was analyzed using SPSS. Descriptive statistics like frequency, percentage was used for describing demographic data as age in year, gender, clinical experience, qualification and department. Chi square test was used to determine the association between knowledge and expressed practices of staff nurses regarding disaster preparedness.

In this study 20 questionnaire were delivered to the staff nurses. It includes the demographic data and knowledge and practices of the participant regarding the disaster preparedness. Data were collected and putted on SPSS version 21 for analysis. Applied descriptive statistics on different variable calculated and graphically portrayed in table and graphs.

Table-1: Demographic Information of the Participants (N=20).

KNOWLEDGE SCORE						
Frequency Distribution		Mean%	Mean	SD	N	Percentage
Gender	Male	68.6%	24.00	9.11	13	65%
	Female	49.0%	17.14	8.38	7	35%
Age	20-40 Years	61.7%	21.60	9.26	20	100%
	41-60 Years	0.0%			0	
	Above 60 Years	0.0%			0	
Clinical Experience	<1	64.0%	22.42	8.45	12	60%
	1-5	58.2%	20.38	10.86	8	40%
	6-10	0.0%			0	
	>10	0.0%			0	
Qualification	Nursing diploma	57.5%	20.13	10.45	8	40%
	B.Sc. Nursing	66.9%	23.43	7.52	7	35%
	Post-graduation in Nursing	61.1%	21.40	11.01	5	25%
	PhD in Nursing	0.0%			0	
Department	Emergency	64.6%	22.60	9.56	5	25%
	General ward	64.9%	22.71	11.22	7	35%
	Triage	82.9%	29.00		1	5%
	Other	53.5%	18.71	7.99	7	35%

Table-2: The overall knowledge score of the study participants.

CRITERIA MEASURE OF KNOWLEDGE SCORE		
Category Score	Percentage	Frequency
ADEQUATE KNOWLEDGE (25-35)	45%	9
MODERATE KNOWLEDGE (13-24)	40%	8
INADEQUATE KNOWLEDGE (0-12)	15%	3
Maximum Score=35		
Minimum Score=0		

The overall knowledge of the study participants was adequate. Table#2 indicates that 45% (n=9) participants were respond positively regarding the knowledge

questions, 40% (n=8) participants had moderate knowledge and 3% (n=4) were did not gave the correct answer about the knowledge questions.

Table-3: The overall practice score of the study participants.

CRITERIA MEASURE OF PRACTICE SCORE		
Category Score	Percentage	Frequency
GOOD (17-25)	55%	11
AVERAGE (9-16)	40%	8
POOR (0-8)	5%	1
Maximum Score=25		
Minimum Score=0		

The overall practice of the study participants was good. Table#3 indicates that 55% (n=11) participants were respond positively regarding the practice questions, 40%

(n=8) participants showed average practice score knowledge and 5% (n=1) were the participants who responded poor.

Table-4: Demographic Information of the Participants (N=20).

PRACTICE SCORE						
Frequency Distribution		Mean %	Mean	SD	N	Percentage
Gender	Male	60.9%	15.23	5.12	13	65%
	Female	75.4%	18.86	3.08	7	35%
Age	20-40 Years	66.0%	16.50	4.76	20	100%
	41-60 Years	0.0%			0	
	Above 60 Years	0.0%			0	
Clinical Experience	<1	62.7%	15.67	5.65	12	60%
	1-5	71.0%	17.75	2.92	8	40%
	6-10	0.0%			0	
	>10	0.0%			0	
Qualification	Nursing diploma	64.5%	16.13	2.80	8	40%
	B.Sc. Nursing	70.3%	17.57	2.37	7	35%
	Post-graduation in Nursing	62.4%	15.60	9.07	5	25%
	PhD in Nursing	0.0%			0	
Department	Emergency	74.4%	18.60	2.41	5	25%
	General ward	69.1%	17.29	2.56	7	35%
	Triage	68.0%	17.00		1	5%
	Other	56.6%	14.14	7.10	7	35%

Graph 1: Diagram showing frequency distribution of gender.

Graph No 2: Diagram showing frequency distribution of age.

Graph No 3: Diagram showing frequency distribution of clinical experience.

Graph 4: Diagram showing frequency distribution of qualification.

Graph 5: Diagram showing frequency distribution of department.

The overall demographic information of the participants as shown in the table#4. The results shows that the participants of this study were staff nurses in which majority were in the age group of 20-40years. The ages of the participants were ranges between (20-40) 60%. The clinical experience of the participants are matter a lot to handle any kind of emergency in disaster. The clinical experience of most of the participants were 60% who were working in the hospital for a period of (<1

years) followed by 40% who was working for the period of 1 to 5 years. Most of the participants who take part in this study were male 65% and 35% were female. The qualifications of the participants who had nursing diploma 40%, B.Sc. nursing participants were 35% and post-graduation were 25%. The study was done from Medeor Hospital, Manesar, Haryana. The study participants were only staff nurse’s total (N=20).

Table-5: Mean, Standard Deviation, Median and Range for overall knowledge and practice among staff nurses.

Descriptive Statistics	Mean	SD	Median	Range
KNOWLEDGE Score	21.60	9.26	18.50	26
PRACTICE Score	16.50	4.76	17.00	23

SD: Standard Deviation

Table 6: In the present research Chi square were applied to measure the significance or association.

Variables	P-Value	Results
Gender -Knowledge	0.370	NS (NA)
Gender -Practice	0.125	NS (NA)
Age -Knowledge	0.297	NS (NA)
Age -Practice	0.807	NS (NA)
Clinical Experience -Knowledge	0.029	NS (NA)
Clinical Experience -Practice	0.662	NS (NA)
Qualification -Knowledge	0.726	NS (NA)
Qualification -Practice	0.235	NS (NA)
Department -Knowledge	0.807	NS (NA)
Department -Practice	0.529	NS (NA)

*NS (Not significant) and NA (No association)

By applying chi square among the demographical variables (gender, age, clinical experience, qualification and department) and questionnaire (knowledge and practice) variables to search association in between them. From the result of the chi square the clinical experience-knowledge p value 0.029, qualification-knowledge p

value 0.726, clinical experience-practice p value 0.662, qualification-practice p value 0.235, department-knowledge p value 0.807 and department-practice p value 0.529, hence among all of them any association were not found.

Table 7: Correlation Between both Tools.

Pearson's Correlation	Pair1	
	KNOWLEDGE Score	PRACTICE Score
Mean	21.60	16.50
SD	9.265	4.763
N	20	
Correlation	0.023	
Table Value	0.444	
P Value	0.924	
Result	Not Significant	

DISCUSSION

Increasingly frequent global disasters are posing threats to human health and life as disasters cause mass causality incidences. The World Health Organization has called for countries to have detailed plans at all levels in order to be prepared for disasters that may arise. Nurses and midwives are frontline workers under stable conditions, but more so during situations of emergencies and crises, working both in pre-hospital as well as in hospital settings. In order to contribute to saving lives and promoting health under such difficult conditions, they need to have the right competencies.

The motive of the present study was to assess the nurse's knowledge and practices regarding disaster preparedness in the Medeor Hospital, Manesar, Haryana.

In overall view of the present study findings revealed the knowledge and practice score for male and female participants was 43% and 57% respectively (Graph No. #1). Study conducted on knowledge and practices on staff nurses regarding disaster preparedness there no significant association was found. Henceforth in the present study results were obtained that the participants were having adequate knowledge about disasters preparedness, what mock drills are and what their

function is during the mock drills. The practices of the participants in the present study were average as compared to knowledge regarding the disaster preparedness. They participants did not know much enough about the mock drill's, there ongoing training; the disasters plan was periodically updated and the practices about disaster preparedness were insufficient. The results show that the overall good practices were 55%.

A comparative study of 4 years undergraduates nursing students was done to assess the educational needs concerning; disaster preparedness and response in Istanbul and Miyazaki. The study reported that most student nurses had no expectations on skills that could be gained from a disaster preparedness and response course/culture of disaster lecture. Nursing students in both cities seem more likely to participate in disaster preparedness and response courses/lectures. Researchers addressed the need to incorporate mass casualty care and disaster management skills into undergraduate curricula. Core contents for nursing curricula in both cities need to be continued. Outcome competencies must be identified and validated through further research

Another study conducted showed the results was found that shows the level of their practices were very negative regarding the disasters preparedness. In another study which is conducted on Nurses Knowledge, attitudes, practices and familiarity regarding disaster and emergency preparedness, the results of her study showed lack of knowledge level of the study participants and the study finding revealed that the practices of participants regarding disaster preparedness was below average level. A study conducted and according to the obtained results of this research, generally preparation against the any emergency and disasters in Tehran's hospital was found very weak. Its mean the practices were not good in selected hospital. Another study was conducted, the result of this study found that PHNs' (public health nurses) ability to practice regarding disaster management was at a moderate level. According to the study, A total of 877 nurses only 44 nurses answer the knowledge-based question and result showed that there was low level of knowledge regarding the emergency preparedness which is dissimilar to present study. This study results showed that nurses perceived that they are not fully prepared for disasters and were not aware of disaster management protocols in the workplace. Many KAP studies conducted of nurses' role in disaster and emergency preparedness. A study undertaken by nurses in Hong Kong the results concluded that nurses are not adequately prepared for disasters, but are aware of the need for such preparation. So that disaster management training should be included in the basic education of nurses.

CONCLUSION

The discussion was organized based on findings of the study. Henceforth, health care providers should go through more practice mock drills to increases the ability to manage the mass causality incidence at the earliest and also to prevent them. By preventing or controlling the mass causality will decrease the fatalities at the time of any event and may lead to more productive life and ameliorate excellence of life.

LIMITATIONS

The present study has some limitations as follows

- Data has been collected from Medeor Hospital, Manesar, Haryana. Data collected was limited so its generalizability of the study is limited. It is recommended for future that all hospitals in a region should be included to take a broader review.
- Sample of the study was short to represent the large population. Therefore, large sample should be taken.
- Cross-sectional design of this study is yet another limitation.
- Convenient sampling is also limitation of the study whereas the probability sampling method can be enhancing the induction of different strata of the participants.
- The problem which faced most of the time during the completing the questionnaire was limitation of

time. The study was conducted in a limited time period of 5 months.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- There should be adequate training of all nurses in both public and private health care setting in order to provide knowledge on how to prepare and handle any emergency situations.
- Disaster plan should be placed in every hospital where nurses and other staff should easily access them and Plan should be available when needed.
- The disaster management committee should make plan and make sure that all staff member should know where the plans are and meet all these plans.
- Every member of staff e.g., head nurses and staff nurses should know their roles, responsibilities and their function during a drill.
- Training program should be made regarding the emergency management and disaster preparedness by the management committee. Some educational program and training practice about the disaster and emergency preparedness should be placed in the nursing curriculum in order to their learning and training preferences.
- Nursing research in disaster is necessary in order to provide information to make evidenced-based decisions regarding practice and education.
- Disaster Management committee should make institution or training centre for the training of staff to handle any kind of emergency.
- All staff should inform about the regularity of the drill and ongoing training.
- The disaster management committee should be knowledge that all plan is regularly maintained and updated.
- Management committee should take responsibilities that all hospital is adequately prepared and plans are ready to use.
- Regular meeting should be continued to check the plan and proper implementation of the plans.
- Communication is very important for success of every plan. The telephone numbers and address of all staff members should be involved in the plan.
- Further researches should be made for maximizing the nursing education and quality of care in these critical situations in the health care setting.
- The above duties should be checked by the disaster management committee and the administration of the hospital.

Strength of the study

The present study has a number of strength which is as follows: This study conducted in the Gurugram, India context which assesses the knowledge and practice of staff nurses regarding the disasters preparedness. Moreover, this study has collected the data on disaster, disaster preparedness process, knowledge and practice variable and as well as demographic variable of the study. In this study the self-administered questionnaire was used which was already been tested for validity and

reliability. The reliability was checked by Split-Half (odd-even) Correlation method for knowledge and practice i.e., 0.918349 and 0.711198 respectively.

Data was collected after the signed of permission letter from the hospital authority and data was collected under supervision of nursing superintendent of the hospital. The rule of Ethical consideration was followed in this study. Anonymity and confidentiality were assured.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I am also very thankful for the staff nurses of Medeor Hospital, Manesar, Haryana, who cooperate me and give necessary information which gave me opportunity to complete my job. I would like to thanks my senior teachers who helped me a lot to complete this study within the limited time.

REFERENCE

- Ibrahim, F. A. A. Nurses Knowledge, attitudes, practices and familiarity regarding disaster and emergency preparedness–Saudi Arabia. *American Journal of Nursing Science*, 2014; 3(2): 18-25.
- Ismail, A., & Saiboon, I. M. Disaster management: a study on knowledge, attitude and practice of emergency nurse and community health nurse. Paper presented at the BMC Public Health, 2012.
- Jakeway, C. C., LaRosa, G., Cary, A., & Schoenfisch, S. The role of public health nurses in emergency preparedness and response: A position paper of the association of state and territorial directors of nursing. *Public Health Nursing*, 25(4), 353-361.
- Labrague, L. J., Yboa, B. C., McEnroe–Petitte, D. M., Loblino, L. R., & Brennan, M. G. B. Disaster preparedness in Philippine nurses. *Journal of nursing scholarship*, 2016; 48(1): 98-105.
- Miller, P. An assessment of emergency department staff knowledge of emergency preparedness: Northern Kentucky University, 2011.
- Moabi, R. M. Knowledge, attitudes and practices of health care workers regarding disaster preparedness at Johannesburg hospital in Gauteng Province, South Africa, 2009.
- Singhal, Y. K., Bhatnagar, R., Lal, B., & Paliwal, B. Knowledge, attitudes, and practices of medical internship students regarding disaster preparedness at a tertiary-care hospital of Udaipur, Rajasthan, India. *International Journal of Medical Science and Public Health*, 2016; 5(8): 1613-1616.
- O'Sullivan, T. L., Dow, D., Turner, M. C., Lemyre, L., Corneil, W., Krewski, D., Amaratunga, C. A. Disaster and emergency management: Canadian nurses' perceptions of preparedness on hospital front lines. *Prehospital and Disaster Medicine*, 2008; 23(3): S11-S18.
- Peoples, K., Gebbie, K., & Hutton, A. An exploration of perceptions of disaster nursing and disaster preparedness among Australian nursing undergraduates. *Health emergency and disaster nursing*, 2016; 3(1): 28-35.
- Putra, A., Petpichetchian, W., & Maneewat, K. Perceived ability to practice in disaster management among public health nurses in Aceh, Indonesia. *Nurse Media Journal of Nursing*, 2011; 1(2): 169-186.
- Ulfat, S., Shaheen, R., Riaz, R., & Said, A. B. Knowledge, Attitude and Practice of Nurses Regarding Disaster Management: A Study from Peshawar KPK.
- Zarei, V. Emergency preparedness of hospitals in Tehran and its relation with crisis management measures. *Health Sciences*, 2016; 5(9S): 471-478.
- Baack, S., & Alfred, D. Nurses' preparedness and perceived competence in managing disasters. *Journal of nursing scholarship*, 2013; 45(3): 281-287.
- Baack, S. T. Analysis of Texas Nurses' Preparedness and Perceived Competence in Managing Disasters, 2011.
- Babaie, J., Ardalan, A., Vatandoost, H., Goya, M. M., & Akbarisari, A. Performance assessment of communicable disease surveillance in disasters: a systematic review. *PLOS Currents Disasters*, 2015.
- Bella Magnaye, R., Muñoz, M. S. L. M., Muñoz, M. A. F., Muñoz, R. G. V., & Muro, J. H. M. The role, preparedness and management of nurses during disasters. *Indexing*, 269.
- Diab, G. M., & Mabrouk, S. M. The effect of guidance booklet on knowledge and attitudes of nurses regarding disaster preparedness at hospitals. *Journal of Nursing Education and Practice*, 2015; 5(9): 17.
- Fung, O. W., Loke, A. Y., & Lai, C. K. Disaster preparedness among Hong Kong nurses. *Journal of advanced nursing*, 2008; 62(6): 698-703.
- Garbutt, S. J., Peltier, J. W., & Fitzpatrick, J. J. Evaluation of an instrument to measure nurses' familiarity with emergency preparedness. *Military medicine*, 2008; 173(11): 1073-1077.
- Brennan L et. al; Major incident planning in South East Thames Region: a survey of medical staff awareness and training *J AccidEmerg Med.*, 1995 Mar; 12(1): 73.